

$$\int_0^{n-1} f(x)dx - \int_0^n f(x)dx \leq S(n) - f(0) - f(n) - \int_0^n f(x)dx \leq \int_1^n f(x) - \int_0^1 f(x)dx = -\int_0^1 f(x)dx$$

$$-\int_{n-1}^n f(x)dx \leq (\dots) \leq \int_{n-1}^n f(x)dx$$

$$\left| S(n) - f(0) - f(n) - \int_0^n f(x)dx \right| \leq \int_{n-1}^n f(x)dx \leq f(n) \quad (3)$$

f kemeyiwshi bolganda da usınday bolıp dálillenedi. Teorema dálillendi.

1-misal. $\int_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} = \ln n + O(1), n \rightarrow +\infty$

Sheshilliwi. Teoremadan kelip shıǵadı, $n \rightarrow +\infty$ da

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} = \int_1^n \frac{dx}{x} + O(1) + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) = \ln n - \ln 1 + O(1) + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) = \ln n + O(1)$$

2-misal. Eger $\alpha > -1$ bolsa $\sum_{k=1}^n k^\alpha - \frac{n^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha+1}$.

Sheshilliwi. Teoremaniń sharti boyınsha.

$$\sum_{k=1}^n k^\alpha = \int_1^n x^\alpha dx + O(1) + O(n^\alpha) = \frac{n^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha+1} - \frac{1}{\alpha+1} + O(1) + O(n^\alpha) = \frac{n^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha+1} \left[1 + O\left(\frac{1}{n^{\alpha+1}}\right) + O\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \right]$$

$$- \frac{n^{\alpha+1}}{\alpha+1} (n \rightarrow \infty).$$

Teorema. Eger $f \in C^{+1}[0; +\infty)$ bolsa, bul jaǵdayda

$$\left| \sum_{k=0}^n f(k) - \int_0^n f(x)dx \right| \leq \|f(0)\| + \int_0^n \|f'(x)\| dx \text{ boladi}$$

Dálillew. $f(k)$ nı tómendegishe ánatamız

$$f(k) = \int_{k-1}^k f(x)dx = \int_{k-1}^k [f(x) + f(k) - f(x)]dx = \int_{k-1}^k f(x)dx + \int_{k-1}^k [f(k) - f(x)]dx = \int_{k-1}^k f(x)dx + g(k)$$

$$g(x) = \int_{k-1}^k [f(k) - f(x)]dx \text{ ni bahalaymız.}$$

Bizge belgili, $f(k) - f(x) = \int_x^k f'(t)dt$, ($k-1 \leq x \leq k$) hám $\|f(k) - f(x)\| \leq \int_{k-1}^k \|f'(t)\|dt$ orınlı.

Bul jerden

$$\|g(k)\| \leq \int_{k-1}^k \|f(k) - f(x)\|dx \leq \int_{k-1}^k \left(\int_{k-1}^k \|f'(t)\|dt \right) dx = \int_{k-1}^k \|f'(t)\|dt \Rightarrow \left| \sum_{k=0}^n f(k) - \int_0^n f(x)dx \right| = \left| f(0) + \sum_{k=1}^n g(k) \right| \leq$$

$$\|f(0)\| + \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{k-1}^k \|f'(t)\|dt = \left\| f(0) + \int_0^n f'(x)dx \right\|$$

Teorema dálillendi.

1-2 teoremlar shekli qosindilar ushin dälillendi. Olardi Qatar ushin da ulıwmalastırıw múmkin

2.6-teorema. Eger

1) $f \in C[0, +\infty)$

2) $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f(n) < \infty,$

3) $\int_0^{\infty} |f(x)| dx < \infty$ bolsa onda

$$\left| \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} f(k) - \int_n^{\infty} f(x) dx \right| \leq |f(n)| + \int_n^{\infty} |f(x)| dx.$$

Mısal; $\sum_{k=n}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^a} \sim \frac{n^{1-a}}{a-1}, n \rightarrow \infty, a > 1.$

Sheshiliwi. $\left| \sum_{k=n}^{\infty} f(k) - \int_n^{\infty} f(x) dx \right| \leq |f(n)| + \int_n^{\infty} |f(x)| dx$ $f(x) = x^{-a}, f'(x) = -ax^{-a-1}.$

$\int_n^{\infty} |f(x)| dx = n^{-a}, \int_n^{\infty} f(x) dx = \frac{n^{-a+1}}{a-1}$ bolğanı ushin $n \rightarrow \infty$ $\sum_{k=n}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^a} = \frac{n^{-a+1}}{a-1} + O(n^{-a}).$

Qosindınıń asimptotasın esaplawğa tiyisli máseller

1-mısal. $S(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{a^k}{x+k}, 0 < a < 1$ nıń $x \rightarrow +\infty$ da asimptotasın tabıń.

Sheshiliwi: $x > k$ bolsa, $\frac{1}{x+k} = \frac{1}{x} - \frac{k}{x^2} + \frac{k^2}{x^3} - \frac{k^3}{x^4} + \dots$ bolğanı ushin, $S(x)$ tı formal tárizde tómendegishe jazıw múmkin:

$S(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_n}{x^n}, A_n = (-1)^n \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n-1} \cdot a^k$ qatardıń $x \rightarrow +\infty$ dagı asimptotalıq ekenligin kórsetemiz;

$S_n(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n A_k \cdot x^{-k}$ dep belgilep alamız

$$S_n(x) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{a^k}{x} - \frac{k a^k}{x^2} + \frac{k^2 a^k}{x^3} - \dots + \frac{(-1)^n k^n a^n}{x^{n+1}} \right) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[1 - \left(-\frac{k}{x} \right)^{n+1} \right] \frac{a^k}{x+k}$$

$x > 0$ de $S(x) - S_n(x)$ ayırmanı bahalaymız:

$$|S(x) - S_n(x)| = \left| \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(-\frac{k}{x} \right)^{n+1} \frac{a^k}{x+k} \right| \leq x^{-n+1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n+1} a^k$$

$C_n = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n+1} a^k < \infty$ bolğanı ushin $|S(x) - S_n(x)| \leq C_n x^{-n+1}, x > 0 \Rightarrow x \rightarrow +\infty$ da

$S(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_n}{x^n}, A_n = (-1)^n \cdot \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k^{n-1} \cdot a^k$ qatardıń asimptotalıq ekenligi kelip shıǵadı.

2-mısal. $S(n) = \sum_{k=0}^n k!$ qosindınıń $n \rightarrow \infty$ da asimptotalıǵın tabıń.

Sheshiliwi. Bul qosindiniń aǵzaları n nómerdiń ósiwi menen tez ósedi, sol sebepli asimptotaniń bas aǵzası qosindiniń aqırǵı aǵzasına teń boladi: yaǵnıy

$S(n) = n!$, $n \rightarrow \infty$. Haqiqatında da, $\frac{S(n)}{n!} = 1 + \frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{n(n-1)} + \dots + \frac{1}{n(n-1)\dots 2 \cdot 1}$ bolǵanı ushın,

$$S(n) = 1 + \frac{1}{n} + O\left(\frac{1}{n^2}\right), n \rightarrow \infty.$$

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